

Management Of Horizontal Root Fracture with Intraradicular Splinting: A Case Report

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Abstract

Root fractures are characterized by a separation of an apical segments, not usually displaced, and a coronal segment, which is often variously displaced. After the impact, healing of pulp and the other damaged tissues depends on patients age, tooth mobility, degree of root formation, location of root fracture, diastasis of fragments and time between trauma & treatment. Depending on the level of the fracture line various treatment modalities may be employed by the clinician to promote healing. Splinting by definition is an appliance used for immobilization of injured or diseased parts and causing teeth heal faster. The intraradicular splinting involves stabilizing fractured root fragment by connecting them internally using a metal splint. In the present case coronal and apical root fragments were endodontically treated under local infiltrative anaesthesia and obturated with master apical k file as intraradicular splint along with Bio-Ceramic sealer to stabilize the root fragments internally. The coronal portion of the tooth was stabilized with the help of stainless-steel wire which was kept for three months. 1-year follow-up examination revealed satisfactory clinical and radiographic findings with hard tissue repair of the fracture line.

Keywords: Root fracture, bio ceramic sealer, intraradicular splinting

Introduction

Root fractures, defined as fractures involving dentine, cementum, pulpal and supportive tissues (e.g., the periodontal ligament and alveolar bone), constitute only 0.5–7% of all dental injuries⁽¹⁾.

Moreover, the age group between 10 and 20 years old is most likely to be affected. The chance of occurrence is more in male patients which may be due to trauma associated with automobile accidents, sports injuries, fights, etc.⁽²⁾ A root fracture is frequently seen in teeth that are permanent and fully erupted having complete formation of the apex. This may be due to the presence of support through bone and periodontium⁽³⁾. Horizontal root fractures are commonly observed in the maxillary anterior region and 75% of these fractures occur in the maxillary central incisors⁽⁴⁾. Root fractures can be broadly classified as

- Horizontal (transverse)
- Vertical

Horizontal root fractures are the most common type and occur mainly in the anterior region of the maxilla (maxillary central incisor region) in fully erupted teeth with complete root formation, owing to a frontal impact⁽⁵⁾.

They occur most commonly in the middle-third and rarely in the apical and coronal-third of the root, they show the highest chances of preservation of pulp vitality as compared to other luxation injuries⁽⁶⁾.

Another rare type of root fracture is a vertical root fracture that extends through the long axis of the root toward the apex. An interdisciplinary and/or multidisciplinary approach may be required for the functional and aesthetic rehabilitation of the tooth following such fractures⁽⁷⁾.

Classification of Tooth Fracture

Horizontal/transverse root fractures are most commonly seen in young adults due to direct physical trauma in the anterior region.

They can be of two types on the basis of:

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Aetiology

The most common reason for root fractures in the permanent dentition is physical trauma caused during falls, fights or sporting events. Any object striking the teeth may also lead to a similar injury. As fights and sporting activities are more common in the first and second decade of life, an increased prevalence of root fractures is observed in a similar age group (11–22 years).

Usually, horizontal root fractures are observed in anterior teeth with direct trauma. In posterior teeth, it usually occurs as a result of indirect trauma. In addition, root fractures may occasionally be caused by parafunctional habits, traumatic occlusion, extensive tooth decay and iatrogenic causes⁽⁸⁾.

Case Report

A 47-year-old male patient came to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics of Chandra Dental College and Hospital with pain and grade I mobility (Miller's classification) #25 and gave history of road traffic accident 1 year ago (fig1). On clinical examination slight discoloration and EPT gave no response and in radiographic examination the left maxillary second premolar shows widening of PDL space and root was fractured horizontally.

In present case root fracture was classified as simple, total, not displaced, located at the junction of middle and apical third (fig2).

Fig. 1 Pre-op Clinical View

As the conventional post preparation demands more dentine expense and requires at least 5mm of GP between the apical ends of the tooth and post, since in this case fracture occurred approximately at 4 to 4.5 mm above the apical end of the root and to establish a proper reinforcement intraradicular splinting was chosen to approximate the fragments (screw action) for a better immobilization and healing of the fracture.

It was decided to attempt root canal treatment followed by an intra-radicular splinting, the treatment plan was explained to the patient and his consent was obtained.

Fig-2 Pre-op Radiographic View

In the first appointment local infiltrative anaesthesia was given and access cavity opening done under rubber dam single canal was found #25, by placing 15-k file into the root canal and working length was recorded with the help of RVG (Fig 3).

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Fig. 3 Working Length Radiograph

The canal was irrigated thoroughly using 3% sodium hypochlorite (Parcan, Septodont, India) and 17% EDTA solution for the removal of remaining pulp tissue and debris, and shaping was done till the apex up to size 60 K file (Dentsply, York, USA) via step back technique.

Root canal was dried with sterile paper points and Calcium Hydroxide (Metapex, Chung cheongbuk-do, Korea) intracanal medicament was placed into the root canal and access cavity was restored with temporary restorative material (Cavit) (DENTSPLY, York, USA). The patient was recalled after three weeks.

In the second appointment patient was asymptomatic, and no sign of pain, inflammation & discharge of pus. The old intra canal medicament was removed with the help of endodontic instruments along with copious irrigation with 3% sodium hypochlorite (Parcan, Septodont, India) and EDTA irrigating solution, a sterile 60 K file was placed up to the working length.

Snug fit of the instrument was assessed and optimal length

was determined. The instrument was weakened at 1mm below the reference point using Diamond disk (Horico Diamante, Berlin, Germany) (fig4).

After that final irrigation of the root canal was done with distilled water and dried with sterile paper points, root canal was filled with Bio- Ceramic sealer as well as the weakened instrument was also scooped with the bio- ceramic sealer. It was then placed within the canal and turned clockwise, until a snug fit was obtained due to binding of the flutes into the dentin.

Fig. 4 Weakening of the File

Fig. 5 Post-obturation

To check the fit of intraradicular splinting and obturation of the root canal, RVG was taken(fig5). For initially complete stabilization and immobilization of #25, extra coronal Stabilization splint was prepared with orthodontic wire (0.30 Gauge) then placed on the tooth (25) for 3 months (fig 6,7,8).

Fig-6 Extra coronal splintingof#25 (clinical view)

Fig.7 Extra coronal splinting of #25 (radiographic view)

Fig-8 Removal of splint

At 12-month follow up patient was asymptomatic and no mobility or periapical changes were noted. The fracture line was clearly visible but no rounding of edges was noted indicating that healing may have occurred by bone and connective tissue deposition(fig9).

Fig-9 At 12 month follow up Radiograph

Discussion

Radicular fractures in permanent teeth are uncommon injuries among dental traumas, being only 0.5-7% of the cases (Flores et al., 2007). Mid-root fractures occur most frequently in the upper anterior teeth due to their position in the arch^(9,10). Management of root fractures can be divided into treatment of apical-third, middle-third and cervical-third fractures.

M A N A G E M E N T	Position of fracture line	Treatment	
	Apical	Watch and observe	
		Retain the segment	Pulp vital
		Surgical extraction	Pulp necrosis
	Middle	Reduction and stabilization	
		Healing	70-80% of intra-alveolar fractures
		Root canal treatment	Pulp necrosis
	Cervical	Poorest chances of healing	
		Reduction & stabilization	Coronal segment is present Fracture below the alveolar bone crest
		Reattachment	Coronal segment is present Fracture at or above the alveolar bone crest
Post crowns		Coronal segment is absent (lost) Fracture above the alveolar bone crest	
Periodontal surgery		Sufficient root length Fracture below the alveolar bone crest Aesthetic result is not required	
Orthodontic extrusion		Sufficient root length Fracture below the alveolar bone crest Aesthetic result is required	
Surgical extrusion		Emergency treatment Fracture below the alveolar bone crest	
Extraction	Other conservative treatments not possible Other conservative treatments failed Poor prognosis		

In this case, a horizontal fracture at the junction of apical and middle third was seen which was treated endodontically followed by immobilization with a rigid K-file (intraradicular splinting). Intraradicular splinting approximates the fracture fragments of root via screw action for a better healing. The file separated at the weakened area was chosen rather than post preparation due to its higher flexibility and rigid nature. And require at least 4 to 5mm GP between the apical end of the root and post. The following picture explains the advantages of an endodontic instrument to fix the separated root fragments over the other post systems^(11,12).

Trauma to the teeth can be transmitted to the supporting structures, which get damaged. This can cause mobility of the teeth. Such mobile teeth may require splinting for a specified

period of time till the supporting tissues heals and the tooth becomes stable. The main objective of splinting is to decrease tooth movement three-dimensionally. Healing of the fracture site will take place by either union with hard tissue or by interposition of connective tissue, fracture is healed by a process which take place over a period of time.

In our case extra coronal splint used, which doesn't require any extra tooth preparations which tends to compromise the already mutilated tooth. Oral Hygiene can be maintained, It is easy to install, repair and remove⁽¹³⁾. Splint is applied for a period of 3 months to ensure sufficient hard tissue consolidation.

The healing events are monitored clinical & radiographically over a period of 3 months, if after this there is no signs of pain, infection, inflammation, bone loss at the apex and around the fracture line of the traumatized tooth extracoronal splint can be removed.

(J.O. Andreasen & F.M. Andreasen)

As the incidence of necrosis in cases of horizontal root fracture is slightly over 20%, it has been suggested that an immediate endodontic intervention should be avoided provided that there are no clinical and /or radiographic pathological signs⁽¹¹⁾.

In the present case root canal treatment was performed before the intraradicular splinting, since the discoloration, no response to EPT, TOP positive, and Pdl space widening. A root-fractured tooth requires an adequate initial intervention and periodic evaluations. Properly treated teeth with horizontal root fractures have a good prognosis^(13,14).

Bioceramic root canal sealer was used in this case, they have gained popularity in recent years due to their unique chemical and physical properties. These sealers are composed of biocompatible materials that mimic the natural composition of tooth structure, making them an ideal choice for root canal treatment. Bioceramic sealers have several physical properties that make them superior to traditional sealers, including excellent sealing ability, dimensional stability, and low solubility. These properties ensure that the sealers provide a tight seal, preventing bacterial leakage and reducing the risk of reinfection. The biocompatibility of bioceramic sealers makes them a safe and effective option for complex root canal treatment and for traumatic tooth.

In contrast, traditional sealers, such as epoxy resin-based sealers, have been found to have several drawbacks, including mutagenicity, cytotoxicity, inflammatory response, and hydrophobicity.

A recent study by Zamparini et al. analyzed the chemical, physical and biological properties of newly introduced premixed bioceramic root canal sealer and found that performed well in terms of sealing ability, biocompatibility, and dimensional stability⁽¹⁵⁾.

Conclusion

Horizontal root fracture following trauma should not be considered as an indication for extraction.

This case highlights the conservative non-surgical

management of horizontal root fractures associated with necrosis of the tooth that allows for aesthetic, functional and economic alternative in developing economies. Depending on the location of fracture line, vitality of pulp and displacement of fractured segment different technique may be selected for the optimal management.

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